

Information Communication Technology (ICT) use in Sports Entrepreneurship Management for the Development of University Sports in South-South Nigeria

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Abstract

This study explored the application of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in sports entrepreneurship management and its role in advancing university sports development across South-South Nigeria. Using a descriptive survey design, the study sampled 407 respondents, including academic staff, students, and sports directors, selected via purposive and random techniques across 11 public universities. A validated questionnaire with reliability coefficients ranging from 0.63 to 0.74 was used for data collection. Results revealed that ICT significantly enhances sports development, particularly in areas such as entrepreneurship management, product availability, and e-commerce. Regression analysis showed that ICT use accounted for 31.5% of the variance in sports development, while ICT through e-commerce explained 72.8% of the variance. The study concludes that integrating ICT tools and training in sports entrepreneurship curricula can improve graduate employability and sports commercialization. It recommends embedding ICT competencies in Human Kinetics programs, better funding, and expanded access to ICT resources for sports development.

Keywords: ICT, Sports Entrepreneurship, University Sports, Sports Management, E-commerce

Introduction

Entrepreneurship has emerged as a key engine for economic revitalization, youth empowerment, and innovation worldwide. In particular, sports entrepreneurship is gaining increasing attention due to its potential to generate income, enhance social cohesion, and promote healthy lifestyles. According to Ratten (2018), the sports industry fosters entrepreneurial creativity through flexible business models and minimal start-up barriers. This development is particularly relevant in Nigeria, where high youth unemployment continues to demand practical, scalable solutions.

With the rapid advancement of Information and Communication Technology (ICT), new opportunities for digital entrepreneurship are transforming the way sports enterprises are created and managed. ICT tools—ranging from mobile apps and e-commerce platforms to data analytics and virtual communication—enable entrepreneurs to reach broader audiences, optimize business operations, and reduce overhead costs (UNESCO, 2004; Institute of Entrepreneurship Development, 2020). The integration of ICT into sports entrepreneurship allows for more efficient delivery of services such as online coaching, virtual competitions, sports product marketing, and digital payment systems.

The university environment presents an ideal setting for nurturing sports entrepreneurship, especially through departments such as Human Kinetics and Health Education. As highlighted by Musa and Yahaya (2014), university-based sports programs help foster physical, social, and emotional development among students. However, gaps persist in infrastructure, funding, and training that hinder the full potential of sports

entrepreneurship. Incorporating ICT into these programs could help bridge these gaps by providing scalable, innovative solutions to sports administration and commercialization.

Despite its relevance, there is limited empirical research on how ICT is currently used in managing sports entrepreneurship within Nigerian universities. Prior studies have highlighted the theoretical benefits of ICT in education and business, but have not sufficiently evaluated its practical application within the sports sector. This study addresses that gap by investigating the extent to which ICT tools are utilized in sports entrepreneurship management and how these tools contribute to sports development in public universities in South-South Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Unemployment among Nigerian youth remains a significant socio-economic concern, with limited access to formal job opportunities. Graduates of Human Kinetics and Health Education programs often face challenges in securing employment, despite the vast potential within the sports industry. While sports entrepreneurship presents a viable pathway to self-employment and economic empowerment, the lack of relevant skills particularly in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) continues to hinder progress.

The evolving nature of the sports industry demands innovative approaches that integrate technology into business models. ICT tools offer significant potential for sports marketing, e-commerce, administration, and performance management. However, in many Nigerian universities, the use of ICT in sports entrepreneurship remains minimal. Institutions often lack the infrastructure, funding, and strategic focus needed to incorporate ICT into sports-related training and practice.

Without structured exposure to ICT in university sports programs, students may graduate without the competencies required to participate effectively in modern sports entrepreneurship. This disconnect contributes to missed opportunities in creating sports-based businesses, commercializing athletic activities, and expanding the reach of university sports.

Therefore, this study seeks to address the critical question: To what extent is ICT being used in sports entrepreneurship management, and how does this influence sports development in public universities across South-South Nigeria?

Purpose of the Study

The primary aim of this study is to assess the extent to which Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is utilized in sports entrepreneurship management and how this contributes to the development of university sports in South-South Nigeria. The study further seeks to explore the role of ICT-driven e-commerce in enhancing entrepreneurial outcomes and sports development within tertiary institutions.

Specifically, the study aims to:

1. Determine the extent to which ICT use in sports entrepreneurship management contributes to the development of sports in public universities in South-South Nigeria.
2. Examine how ICT-based e-commerce platforms influence sports entrepreneurship and development in university settings.
3. Identify existing limitations in the adoption of ICT tools for sports entrepreneurship within Human Kinetics and Sports Directorate departments.
4. Assess the potential of ICT to enhance graduate employability through the commercialization of sports-related activities.

Research Questions

This study is guided by the following research questions:

1. To what extent does the use of ICT in sports entrepreneurship management enhance sports development in universities in South-South Nigeria?
2. To what extent does the use of ICT through e-commerce support sports development in universities in South-South Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at the 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between ICT use in sports entrepreneurship management and sports development in universities in South-South Nigeria.
2. ICT use through e-commerce does not significantly influence sports development in universities in South-South Nigeria.

Research Design

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design to explore how Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is used in sports entrepreneurship management to foster university sports development in South-South Nigeria. This design was considered appropriate as it enabled the collection of detailed data from a large population without manipulation of variables (McCombes, 2022).

Population of the Study

The target population comprised 2,311 individuals drawn from eleven public universities located across Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo, and Rivers States. This population included:

- 2,116 students from the Departments of Human Kinetics, Recreation, and Sports Science
- 120 academic staff from the same departments
- 75 staff members from the Sports Directorates

(Data source: ICT Directorates of the respective universities)

Sample Size and Sampling Techniques

A total sample of 407 participants was selected for the study. The sample consisted of:

- 212 students, selected using simple random sampling via the balloting method
- 120 academic staff and 75 Sports Directorate staff, selected using purposive sampling due to their small population size and relevance to the study

From each university (except the University of Delta, Agbor), 21 students were randomly chosen. In the case of the University of Delta, all three Human Kinetics students were included due to their small number. The balloting method involved writing "Yes" or "No" on slips of paper, placing them in a bag, and selecting respondents who picked "Yes."

Universities were selected based on their possession of active Human Kinetics and Sports Science departments, ensuring relevance to the study objectives.

Research Instrument

The primary instrument for data collection was a researcher-designed questionnaire titled: "Information Communication Technology Use in Sports Entrepreneurship Management Toward Sports Development in South-South Nigerian Universities (ICTISEM)"

The instrument consisted of two sections:

- Section A: Collected demographic information (university, state, respondent category)
- Section B: Originally 56 items, reduced to 49 after factor analysis, covering themes such as ICT use, e-commerce, product availability, and sports development

A four-point Likert scale was used:

Very High (4), High (3), Low (2), Very Low (1)

Validity of the Instrument

The instrument was subjected to face, content, and construct validity processes:

- Face and content validity were ensured by experts in Health Education and Measurement & Evaluation at Delta State University, Abraka.
- Construct validity was verified using factor analysis. Only items with factor loadings above 0.50 were retained, with ICT-related items ranging from 0.58 to 0.97.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the instrument was confirmed using Cronbach's Alpha after administering the questionnaire to 50 respondents from the University of Benin (excluded from the study area):

- ICT in sports entrepreneurship: 0.74
- E-commerce for sports development: 0.63
- Product availability: 0.65

These values indicated acceptable levels of internal consistency.

Method of Data Collection

A formal letter of introduction was issued by the Department of Human Kinetics, Recreation and Sports Science, stating that the study was strictly for academic purposes. With the assistance of six trained research assistants (one per state), the questionnaires were personally administered and retrieved from respondents. Follow-up visits ensured a 100% return rate.

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to standard ethical guidelines:

- Informed consent was obtained from all participants
- Participation was voluntary and anonymous
- Respondents were assured of confidentiality and the academic purpose of the study
- No physical or psychological harm was involved

Method of Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) to answer research questions while inferential statistics using multiple regression analysis via SPSS Version 26 was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 significance level.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1

To what extent does the use of ICT in sports entrepreneurship management enhance sports development in universities in South-South Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation on Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in sports entrepreneurship management on sports development in the universities in South-South Nigeria.

N=407

S/N	Items	VH	H	L	VL	Mean	SD	Decision
1	The extent to which ICT aids sports entrepreneurship management is	292 (71.7%)	77 (18.9%)	21 (5.2%)	17 (4.2%)	3.58	0.77	High
2	The extent to which sports entrepreneurship management benefits from ICT is	311 (76.4%)	61 (15%)	29 (7.1%)	6 (1.5%)	3.66	0.67	High
3	The extent to which ICT in sports entrepreneurship management would develop sports is	305 (74.9%)	68 (16.7%)	16 (3.9%)	18 (4.4%)	3.62	0.76	High
4	The extent to which Nigeria universities deploy ICT in sports is	7 (1.7%)	37 (9.1%)	288 (70.8%)	75 (18.4%)	1.94	0.58	Low
5	The extent to which electricity is provided to enable ICT engagement in Nigeria universities for sports entrepreneurship management is	11 (2.7%)	28 (6.9%)	188 (46.2%)	180 (44.2%)	1.68	0.72	Low
Grand Mean						2.90	0.70	High

Summary of Findings:

Table 1 revealed that respondents largely agreed that ICT significantly contributes to sports entrepreneurship management in universities. The first three items received high mean scores ranging from 3.58 to 3.66, indicating strong agreement on the positive impact of ICT on sports development. However, responses to items on electricity supply and institutional deployment of ICT scored low (means of 1.94 and 1.68, respectively), suggesting infrastructural limitations.

Grand Mean: 2.90, which is above the benchmark of 2.50, showing that overall, respondents perceived the use of ICT in sports entrepreneurship management as highly beneficial to sports development.

Research Question 2

To what extent does the use of ICT in sports entrepreneurship management through e-commerce support sports development in universities in South-South Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation on ICT in sports entrepreneurship management through e-commerce on sports development in the universities.

N=407

S/N	Items	VH	H	L	VL	Mean	SD	Decision
1	The extent to which ICT aids sports entrepreneurship management is	292 (71.7%)	77 (18.9%)	21 (5.2%)	17 (4.2%)	3.58	0.77	High
2	The extent to which sports entrepreneurship management benefits from ICT is	311 (76.4%)	61 (15%)	29 (7.1%)	6 (1.5%)	3.66	0.67	High
3	The extent to which ICT in sports entrepreneurship management would develop sports is	305 (74.9%)	68 (16.7%)	16 (3.9%)	18 (4.4%)	3.62	0.76	High
4	The extent to which Nigeria universities deploy ICT in sports is	7 (1.7%)	37 (9.1%)	288 (70.8%)	75 (18.4%)	1.94	0.58	Low
5	The extent to which electricity is provided to enable ICT engagement in Nigeria universities for sports entrepreneurship management is	11 (2.7%)	28 (6.9%)	188 (46.2%)	180 (44.2%)	1.68	0.72	Low
Grand Mean						2.90	0.70	High

Summary of Findings:

As shown in Table 2, all items assessing the role of e-commerce in sports entrepreneurship management received high mean scores, ranging from 3.60 to 3.64. These findings indicate that respondents believe ICT-driven e-commerce—such as Point-of-Sale (POS) systems, online shopping, and e-banking—can significantly improve efficiency and commercialization in university sports programs.

Grand Mean: 3.62, indicating a strong consensus on the positive contribution of e-commerce to sports development in the universities.

Hypothesis 1

ICT in sports entrepreneurship management would not significantly develop sports in universities in South-South Nigeria.

Table 3: Linear regression analysis on Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in sports entrepreneurship management and sports development in the universities.

Model Summary					
R	R-Square	Adjusted R ²	Std Error of the Estimate		
0.562	0.315	0.314	4.223		
ANOVA					
	Sum of Square	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	3324.929	1	3324.929	186.502	0.000
Residual	7220.275	405	17.828		
Total	10545.204	406			
Coefficients					
Unstandardized Coefficient			Standardized Coefficient		
	B	Std Error	B	T	Sig.
(Constant)	10.009	2.057		4.866	0.000
ICT in sports Entrepreneurship	1.929	0.141	0.562	13.657	0.000

The result in table 3, shows a linear regression output on Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in sports entrepreneurship management and sports development in the universities in South-South Nigeria. The computed F-Value of 186.502 and a P-Value of 0.000. Testing the hypothesis at an alpha level of 0.05, the P-Value of 0.000 was less than the alpha level of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implied that Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in sports entrepreneurship management would significantly enhance sports development in the universities in South-South Nigeria.

The R-Square Value of 0.315 indicates that 31.5% of variance in sports development in the universities was accounted for Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in sports entrepreneurship management. The Unstandardized Coefficient (B) for sports development in the universities from ICT in sports entrepreneurship management was 1.929. The Standardized Coefficient (β) was 0.562, $t = 13.657$. Therefore, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in sports entrepreneurship management was significant at an alpha level of 0.05.

ICT use in sports entrepreneurship management has a statistically significant effect on sports development. Approximately 31.5% of the variance in sports development can be attributed to the use of ICT in sports entrepreneurship management. This indicates a moderate but meaningful relationship.

Hypothesis 2

ICT use in sports entrepreneurship management through e-commerce would not significantly develop sports in universities in South-South Nigeria.

Table 4: Linear regression analysis on Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in sports entrepreneurship management toward e-commerce and sports development in the universities.

Model Summary					
R	R-Square	Adjusted R ²	Std Error of the Estimate		
0.853	0.728	0.727	2.66104		
ANOVA					
	Sum of Square	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	7677.355	1	7677.355	1084.202	0.000
Residual	2867.849	405	7.081		
Total	10545.204	406			
Coefficients					
	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient		
	B	Std Error	B	T	Sig.
(Constant)	12.708	0.778		16.333	0.000
ICT in sports Entrepreneurship towards e-commerce	2.327	0.071	0.853	32.927	0.000

Dependent Variable: Sports Development

Table 4 shows a linear regression output of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in sports entrepreneurship management towards e-commerce and sports development in the universities in South-South Nigeria with the computed F – Value of 1084.202 and a P – Value of 0.000. Testing the null hypothesis at an alpha level of 0.05, the P – Value of 0.000 was less than the alpha value of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implied that Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in sports entrepreneurship management towards e-commerce would significantly improve sports development in the universities in South-South Nigeria.

The R – Square Value of 0.728 indicates that 72.8% of the variance in sports development in the universities was accounted for by Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in sports entrepreneurship management towards e-commerce. The Unstandardized Coefficient (B) for sports development in the universities was 2.327 and the Standardized Coefficient (β) was 0.071, $t = 32.927$. Therefore, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in sports entrepreneurship management was significant at an alpha level of 0.05

ICT use through e-commerce has a strong and statistically significant impact on sports development, accounting for 72.8% of the observed variance. This underscores the transformative role of digital platforms in sports entrepreneurship and university-level sport commercialization.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study demonstrate a strong and significant relationship between the use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in sports entrepreneurship management and the development of university sports in South-South Nigeria. Both descriptive and inferential results point to a high perceived benefit of ICT tools especially in areas such as online transactions, digital engagement, and performance tracking for improving the efficiency, accessibility, and reach of sports activities across university campuses.

This result aligns with the assertions of Abbah and Ogwo (2020), who emphasized that ICT enables innovative marketing, distribution, and branding strategies in the sports sector. Their view that sports entrepreneurs should develop digital competencies is particularly relevant, considering the potential for ICT to support scalable, low-cost ventures, especially for recent graduates of Human Kinetics programs. Similarly, Okeke (2014) recognized the role of ICT in expanding entrepreneurial activities across Nigeria through virtual storefronts, digital promotions, and increased market access.

The study also corroborates Ratten's (2010, 2012, 2018) theory of sports-based entrepreneurship, which holds that innovation driven by technology and market dynamics is a key catalyst for the growth of the sports industry. The significant impact observed in this study, especially in the e-commerce dimension ($R^2 = 0.728$), suggests that digital platforms are not just add-ons but core to modern sports business development.

Moreover, the findings support Uzoamaka, Abbah, and Igwe (2019), who found that ICT tools significantly enhance entrepreneurial efforts among Physical Education professionals. Their study, though focused on Anambra State, found that access to digital systems improved entrepreneurial confidence, income generation, and service delivery. This present study reinforces those insights in a broader regional context across South-South Nigeria.

However, despite these positive trends, respondents highlighted infrastructural challenges such as erratic electricity and limited institutional ICT deployment, echoing concerns raised by West et al. (2016) and Gogoi (2019). These limitations may undermine the scalability and sustainability of ICT-based sports entrepreneurship unless addressed through policy intervention, increased funding, and capacity building.

Interestingly, the high significance of e-commerce tools in this study suggests a shift in how sports-related goods and services are accessed and delivered within academic environments. With platforms enabling online shopping, mobile banking, and digital ticketing, students and staff are becoming both consumers and contributors in a growing virtual sports economy. This dynamic supports Mohapatra (2013) and Zwass (2014), who highlighted the digitalization of commerce as a game-changer for entrepreneurial ecosystems.

In sum, the integration of ICT into university sports entrepreneurship has a substantial impact on sports development outcomes. It enables innovation, commercial engagement, and improved infrastructure while also presenting new pathways for graduate self-employment and institutional revenue generation.

Conclusion

The findings of this study establish that Information and Communication Technology (ICT) plays a pivotal role in advancing sports entrepreneurship and development in universities across South-South Nigeria. The use of ICT tools in managing sports entrepreneurship activities was shown to significantly enhance operational efficiency, increase opportunities for commercialization, and promote self-employment among graduates of Human Kinetics and Sports-related programs.

The study further revealed that ICT-driven e-commerce is a particularly powerful enabler, contributing substantially to digital marketing, virtual service delivery, and online transaction systems within university sports. While infrastructural limitations such as poor electricity and limited ICT access remain barriers, the overall perception and measurable impact of ICT use on sports development were highly positive.

Given the rapid growth of the digital economy and the evolving nature of the sports industry, there is an urgent need for institutions to equip students and sports administrators with relevant ICT competencies. Doing so will not only enhance sports programs but also improve employability, foster innovation, and support national goals for economic development through sports.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. Departments of Human Kinetics and Sports Science should embed ICT training—particularly in entrepreneurship and e-commerce—into their academic programs to prepare students for emerging opportunities in digital sports management.
2. University management, in collaboration with education and sports ministries, should provide adequate funding for ICT tools, software, and reliable power supply to enhance technology use in sports entrepreneurship.
3. Periodic training, workshops, and seminars should be organized for academic staff, coaches, and Sports Directorate personnel on current ICT tools and digital innovations applicable in sports entrepreneurship.
4. National sports and education policy frameworks should explicitly promote the integration of ICT in university sports programs, while also encouraging partnerships with technology firms and sports brands to provide mentorship, sponsorships, and digital infrastructure.
5. Universities should establish innovation hubs or sports entrepreneurship centers that leverage ICT to support students in launching start-ups, accessing virtual marketplaces, and building scalable sports-related ventures.

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